

Homestay Development Strategies in Cibodas Village

Ramang H Demolingo¹, Natasha Erinda Putri Moniaga², Subur Karyatun³, Kadek Wiweka⁴

^{1,3}Universitas Nasional, , Jakarta

² Universitas Udayana, Denpasar

⁴Universite d'Angers, Angers

ABSTRACT: Rural areas have quite unique opportunities to attract tourists by building relationships between them and their cultural, historical, ethnic and geographical roots. However, currently the existing homestay has not been included into tourist' package products, so that it can become a tourist attraction for tourists. This phenomenon causes existing homestays to only be used as accommodation or accommodation facilities. In fact, homestays can also offer a variety of interesting activities related to the culture and social life of the local community. Therefore, in developing a homestay it is very important to involve the local community as a tourist attraction. The purpose of this study is to identify the potential of the Cibodas village as an educational tourist attraction. In addition, to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges of developing homestay in Cibodas tourism village as an educational empowerment attraction based on community empowerment as well. The last one is to formulate a homestay development strategy. In order for this research could be conducted thoroughly and achieves goals that are in accordance to the expectations of the researcher, multi-method approach of qualitative and quantitative method will be applied.

KEYWORDS- rural areas, homestay, educational-tourism, Cibodas Village

I. INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of tourism and tourists has developed and evolved rapidly, both as a "new" scientific cluster, a field of research studies, modern industry, even if viewed from a wider theoretical and practical side. Wiweka and Arcana (2017) note that the phenomenon of the activity of moving a person from their origin to destination with varying motivations has been started since 4,000 BC (BC) by the Sumerians during the Babylonian era, and is growing. In the 17th and 18th centuries in Western Europe with the term "Grand Tour". Through this Tourism Village, rural communities can revive and maintain their entire culture of local wisdom and can be reconstructed through: (a) utilizing positive values derived from interactions with urban tourists and (b) managing or reducing negative values originating from tourists who come.

The concept of developing a Tourism Village is an effort to increase village economic growth by utilizing the village's local potential, namely natural and cultural potential as a tourist attraction. Therefore, tourism development through the Tourism Village is one of the strategies that can be said to be effective, this is because Indonesia has considerable potential and Tourism Village is also believed to be able to channel the economic benefits of tourism directly to the local community. Various ministries are encouraged to support the ministry of tourism's program in a comprehensive and integrated manner. Based on data from the Ministry of Villages (2016) regarding the development of underdeveloped areas and transmigration, Indonesia has 74,954 potential villages and 277 rural areas that can be developed into tourism villages. However, several challenges such as 122 underdeveloped areas, 58 conflict-prone districts, 57 food-insecure districts and 75 disaster-prone districts still require a special strategy so that they can be developed into Tourism Villages. The following is an illustration of the potential of villages that can be developed into tourist villages in Indonesia.

Table 1Actual Condition of Tourist Villages Potential in Indonesia

Category	Total
Village	74.954
Outmost Districts in 41 Reg (Priority Location)	187
Conflict Prone Regency	58
Famine Prone Regency	57
Disaster Prone Regency	75
Underdeveloped Regions	122

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

Rural Areas	277
Transmigration Area	619

Source: Ministry of Rural Areas, 2016

However, from the existing 74 thousand villages, seen from the village progress index, some villages in Indonesia are still in poor condition. This can be seen from the fact that most villages are still classified as underdeveloped and very underdeveloped.

Table 2 Village Development Condition in Indonesia

Village Development Level	Total
Independent Village	173 (0,23%)
Progressive Village	3.610 (4,83%)
Developing Village	22.916 (30,66%)
Underdeveloped Village	33.948 (45,41%)
Very Underdeveloped Village	22.916 (30,66%)

Source: Kementerian PUPR, 2017

There are several aspects that need to be developed to support the Tourism Village, namely the tourist attractions of a village, doable distance, the carrying capacity of facilities and infrastructure, belief systems and society (religion and culture). Of the 74,954 villages owned by Indonesia, 1,902 villages that have been mapped have the potential to be developed as Tourism Villages. Among them are 787 Marine Tourism Villages, 576 River Tourism Villages, 165 Irrigation Tourism Villages, and 374 Lake Tourism Villages.

Figure 1 The amount of potential village to be developed as village tourism

Source: Ministry of Rural Areas, 2017

The tourism village that is currently developing is Cibodas Tourism Village, which is an agricultural area located in the Lembang area, which is located in a hilly area. In general, the condition of the village land is very fertile. Most of the people of Cibodas Village work as farmers. Agricultural land in this village area is 433.72 ha / m². Meanwhile, the plantation area is 351 ha / m². The land area used as offices is 0.3 ha / m². The rest of the land is used as a residential area of 111.5 ha / m², conservation forest of 32 ha / m², and other public infrastructure of 0.92 ha / m².

The main livelihood of the people of Cibodas Village is from the agricultural sector. Especially those with great potential are food crops and plantations. In addition, the forestry potential of this village is quite potential. Another sector that is also very potential to be developed is livestock. Currently, agriculture and plantations are starting to be used as tourist attractions. In addition, local people have also begun to realize the benefits of tourism development in their village.

Currently, to be able to provide comfort and convenience for visiting tourists, the Cibodas tourism village manager continues to complete its facilities and infrastructure. In particular, lodging facilities when tourists enjoy the various natural tourist attractions that Cibodas tourist village offers, it also aims to hold tourists staying longer in Cibodas Tourism Village. The local accommodation facilities provided in Desa Wisata are known as homestays. However, currently the existing homestays have not been packaged into tourist products, so they can become a tourist attraction for tourists. This phenomenon causes existing homestays to be used only as accommodation or lodging facilities. In fact, homestays can also offer a variety of interesting

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

activities related to the culture and social life of local communities. Therefore, in developing a homestay it is very important to involve local communities as a tourist attraction.

Based on the background that has been described above, issues related to community empowerment in the logging of tourist villages have become an interesting issue at this time. Therefore, the authors want to research, provide information, and write into a scientific study with the theme "Homestay Development Strategy in Cibodas Village"

1.1 Main Problems

Based on the empirical phenomena that have been described in the background section, and various related references contained in Chapter II, the identification carried out by researchers in this study includes the phenomenon of propaganda, digital marketing, tourist destinations, and social media. Based on this background, in outline the problem of this research is to examine the "homestay development strategy in Cibodas tourism village as a community empowerment-based educational tourism attraction". From the background and problem identification above, the researcher formulates the main problems that are closely related to the topics discussed, namely:

1. What are the potentials of Cibodas Village as a Tourism Village?
2. Homestay in Cibodas tourism village as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tours?
3. What is the strategy for developing a homestay in the Cibodas tourism village as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tours?

1.2 Research Aims

Based on the formula; problems that have been designed, then to support the research, the researcher compiles research objectives which can be described as follows:

1. To identify the potential of Cibodas Village as a Tourism Village.
2. To identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges of developing a homestay in Cibodas tourism village as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tourism.
3. To formulate a homestay development strategy in Cibodas tourism village as a community empowerment-based educational tourism attraction.

1.3 Research Benefits

This research is expected to provide benefits for research and other parties interested in this research. The expected research benefits are:

1.1.1 Theoretical Benefits

1. Can be useful for academics as reference material who are interested in this field of study.
2. Can add and contribute explanations to the theory of homestay development as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tours.

1.1.2 Practical Benefits

1. Being a material for consideration for stakeholders, especially for officials of Cibodas Tourism Village, West Bandung Regency in developing homestays as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tours
2. Contribute to the provision of a data base for the central government and stakeholders.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Literature Review

This previous research has become one of the writer's references in conducting research so that the author can enrich the theory used in assessing the research undertaken. The following is previous research in the form of several journals related to the research conducted by the author:

1. Andini, N. (2013). Community Organizing in Agro-Tourism Development in Tourism Villages. This research found that there are some tourist markets who have the motivation to seek experiences related to Tourism Village, especially those that offer traditional agricultural experiences. This research also shows how tourists feel value for money for the programs they carry out in agro-tourism destinations;
2. In addition, research by Dewi, M. H. U. (2013). Related to the development of tourism villages based on the participation of local communities in the Tourism Village, it strengthens the hypothesis of this research, where the community-based tourism model is still an attraction for special interest tourists. Especially for those who want to seek experiences related to interactions with local communities, mingle with tourism-conscious groups, and see how the local government develops a village as a tourist destination.
3. While Stone, L. S., & Stone, T. M. (2011). In his research, Community-based tourism enterprises, shows that local people are a potential attraction, especially when viewed from the social ludomania side.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

1) Tourism Requirements

According to Yoeti (2003), the requirements for a trip are referred to as a tourism trip if:

- a. Travel is made from one place to another, outside the place where the person usually lives
- b. The purpose of traveling is solely for fun, and not earning a living in the place or country he is visiting.
- c. Solely as consumers in the places visited.

Tourism Village

In line with the dynamics, the movement of tourism development has penetrated into various terms such as, sustainable tourism development, rural tourism, ecotourism, which is a tourism development approach that seeks to ensure that tourism can be implemented in non-urban tourist destinations. One of the alternative tourism development approaches is a tourist village for sustainable rural development in the tourism sector (Zakaria and Suprihardjo, 2014: 2).

Tapiador notes the European Commission's definition of rural areas is 'a spatial phenomenon that extends across territories, landscapes, natural areas, agricultural land, villages and other major urban centers, industrializing pockets and regional centers. It encompasses diverse and complex economic and social structures. It is the home of a great wealth of natural and cultural resources and traditions. It is becoming more important as a place of relaxation and relaxing activities' (Tapiador, 2007: 1).

Based on this opinion, it can be said that a tourist village is a rural area where the inhabitants have traditions and culture such as local culinary delights and pristine agricultural systems. The beauty of nature and the environment are also important factors that become the attraction or uniqueness for tourists to visit. This must also be supported by supporting facilities such as accommodation and additional services that can facilitate tourists in carrying out tourism activities (<http://www.central-java-tourism.com>, 2012). The tourism sector will support infrastructure improvements in the village to support tourist needs. In addition, tourism in the village also adapts to environmental conditions and village communities such as nature and culture tourism (Holland, Burian, & Dixey, 2003).

2) Rural Tourism

According to (Nusstiawan, 2012), rural tourism is able to provide social benefits for rural communities such as opportunities to interact with people from outside the village, the ability to socialize, and open broader insights about the world. In addition, rural tourism is also able to provide economic benefits. Rural tourism activities, among others, can take advantage of fishing villages, agricultural land, livestock and plantation land.

3) Home Stay

Homestay is a type of accommodation originating from people's houses whose facilities and facilities have been upgraded as lodging for rent to tourists. Homestay locations are generally close to tourist attractions. The existence of a homestay is not only a place to stay, but also a place to learn about local culture.

Regulation of the Minister of Tourism and Creative Economy of the Republic of Indonesia Number 9 of 2014 concerning Tourism Cottage Business Standards, states that the Pondok Wisata / Homestay Business is the provision of accommodation in the form of residential buildings that are occupied by their owners and partially used for rent by providing opportunities for tourists to interact in everyday life of the owner.

Basically, homestays in Indonesia are located in tourist villages, which are residents' homes that are prepared for tourists to stay. Tourists will live under one roof with local residents, follow routines, and experience what life is like there.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order for this research to be focused and achieve the objectives in accordance with the wishes of the researcher, the researcher uses a combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches or what is commonly known as "multi-method". "Mixed methods is a procedure for collecting, analyzing, and" mixing "quantitative and qualitative methods in one study or series of research to understand research problems" (Creswell, 2012: 535). This method is used because in this study it produces two types of data, namely quantitative data and qualitative data. The basic assumption is that the use of quantitative and qualitative methods in combination provides a better understanding of the research problem and question than the method itself.

Quantitative data is data that produces specific numbers that can be analyzed statistically, can produce results to assess the frequency and magnitude of trends, and can provide useful information if it is to describe trends about a large number of people" (Creswell, 2012: 548). The quantitative approach to this research is carried out by distributing questionnaires to tourists who stay at the homestay and visit Cibodas Village, this survey is to determine the views of tourists on the potential of the homestay as a tourist attraction and to determine the ATP and WTP of tourists. In addition, a questionnaire will also be carried out for local communities to survey local community involvement in the development of tourism products in Cibodas Village.

Meanwhile, "Qualitative data such as open interviews that give the actual words of the people in the research, offer many different perspectives on the research topic and provide a complex picture of the situation" (Creswell, 2012: 548). The qualitative approach to this research is carried out by non-participant observation where the researcher is not involved and only becomes an observer, which aims to study and interpret the content or substance of the tourism products offered in Cibodas Tourism Village and the

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

homestays in the Village. Further data collection was carried out by means of interviews or informal conversations guided by instruments or interview guides related to the information needed with the Village apparatus (Village apparatus), local communities, tourism offices, and tourists.

Furthermore, the researcher will take a sample from a group of population to then represent it entirely. The point is that respondents as a sample will represent the entire population. So that with a group of respondents as a sample, researchers do not need to examine all existing populations.

Figure 3.1 The Model

Tujuan Penelitian	Variabel				Time horizon
	Type	Method	Analysis	Observation	
T-1	Verification	Survey Description	Cibodas Village as a potential tourist village	Cibodas Village	One Shoot Cross Section
T-2	Verification	Survey Description	Cibodas Village Homestay as a potential educational tourism attraction	Homestay at Cibodas Village	One Shoot Cross Section
T-3	Verification	Survey Description	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges of developing a homestay in Cibodas tourist village as an attraction for community empowerment-based educational tourism.	Homestay at Cibodas Village and the local communities	One Shoot Cross Section
T-4	Verification	Survey Description	Homestay development strategy in Cibodas tourism village as a community empowerment-based educational tourism attraction	Homestay at Cibodas Village and the local communities	One Shoot Cross Section

1. Key Informants

The key informants in this study were tourists who visited the Cibodas Tourism Village and who stayed at the Homestay, in addition to all the managers of Cibodas Tourism Village and Homestay.

2. Research Focus

In the Thesis Guidelines, Kusmayadi (2013: 25) states that, "The operational definition is the definition of a concept given by a researcher to the person, group, or event being studied in the form of criteria or indicators that can be tested empirically".

Figure 3.2 Operationalization Variable

Variable	Concept	Dimension	Indicator	Measurement	Scale
Community Base Tourism	CBT (Community - Based Tourism) is a tourist assessment of the concept of developing a tourist destination involving local communities, tourism conscious groups, and local governments in its development (Bittar & Prideaux, 2017; Blackstock, 2005; Stone & Stone, 2011; Taylor, 2017) .	Involvement of local communities	Activities perception, involvement of local communities	Activities perception level, involvement of local communities	Ordinal
		Travel conscious group	Activities perception, involvement of local communities	Activities perception level, involvement of local communities	Ordinal
		Local government	Activities perception, involvement of local government	Activities perception level, involvement of local government	Ordinal

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

Tourist Village	Tourism Village is a tourist assessment regarding the form of integration between attractions, accommodation and supporting facilities that are presented in a structure of community life that integrates with prevailing ways and traditions (Andini, 2013; Bowler, et al., 2002; Bramwell, 1994; Briedenhann & Wickens, 2004; Dewi, 2013).	Attraction	Perception of Tourist Attraction	Perception Level of Tourist Attraction	Ordinal
		Tourism Activity	Perception of Tourist Attraction	Perception Level of Tourist Attraction	Ordinal
		Accommodation	Perception of Accommodation	Perception Level of Accommodation	Ordinal
		Amenities	Perception of Amenities	Perception Level of Amenities	Ordinal
		The socio-cultural life of the local communities	Perception of the socio-cultural life of the local communities	Perception level of the socio-cultural life of the local communities	Ordinal

2. Data Analysis Method

According to Creswell (2012), states that, "Triangulation is two sources of data and these phenomena. Refinement in research questions will come from combining the strengths of one type of method and neutralizing the weaknesses of another. This means that researchers can improve their investigations by collecting and aggregating (or integrating) different types of data related to the same phenomenon."

1) Source Triangulation

To test the credibility of the data, this is done by checking the data that has been obtained through several sources. For example, to see the potential of Cibodas Village as a Tourism Village, and the potential of Homestay in Cibodas Tourism Village as a Main Tourist Attraction, data collection and testing can be done through observation and interpretation of existing facts and realities, as well as comments or views from the speakers. Meanwhile, to see how ATP and WTP of visiting tourists, confirmation is done through a questionnaire. The data that has been analyzed by the researcher will produce a conclusion through these two data sources.

2) Technic Triangulation

Technique triangulation to test the credibility of the data is done by checking the data from the same source with different techniques. For example, data is obtained by interview, then checked by observation, documentation or questionnaire. If the data credibility testing technique results in different data, the researcher will conduct further discussions with the relevant data source or other, to ensure which data is considered correct. Or maybe everything is right, because the point of view is different.

3) Time Triangulation

Time also often affects the credibility of data. The data collected by interviewing techniques in the morning when the informant is still fresh, there are not many problems that will provide more valid data so that it is more credible. For that, in order to test the credibility of the data, it can be done by checking by interview, observation, or other techniques in different times or situations. If the test results produce different data, then it is done repeatedly so that data certainty is found. Triangulation can also be done by checking the results of research, from other researchers who are given the task of collecting data.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General Information of the research location

1. Location and Surface Area:

Cibodas Village is located in Lembang District, West Bandung Regency. The area of this village is around 1,273.44 Ha, located at an altitude of 1260 M above sea level. Rainfall 177.5 mm / year with an average temperature of 19 to 22 ° C.

The boundaries of Cibodas Village are:

North side: Wangunharja Village

South side: Cimenyan Village

East side: Suntenjaya Village

West side: Langensari Village

Topography and soil conditions:

Cibodas Village, located in a hilly area. In general, the condition of the village soil is fertile. Most of the people of Cibodas Village work as farmers. Agricultural land in this village area is 433.72 ha / m². Meanwhile, the plantation area is 351 ha / m². The

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

land area used as offices is 0.3 ha / m². The rest of the land is used as a residential area of 111.5 ha / m², conservation forest of 32 ha / m², and other public infrastructure of 0.92 ha / m².

Transportation: The distance from Cibodas Village to the subdistrict capital is 8 Km. Travel time to the subdistrict capital by motor vehicle is 0.5 hours. There are 29 public vehicles available to the subdistrict capital. In addition there is also transportation in the form of ojek, as many as 6 ojek bases.

Governance

Cibodas Village is divided into 3 hamlets, 17 Rukun Warga (RW) areas, and 66 Rukun Tetangga (RT) areas with a total of 2959 households.

Hamlet 1 consists of 6 RWs, namely RW 01, RW 16 (expansion of RW 01), RW 02, RW 03, RW 14 (expansion of RW 03), and RW 04. Dusun 2 consists of 5 RWs, namely RW 05, RW 06, RW 07, RW 08, RW 17 (expansion from RW 06) Dusun 3 which consists of 6 RWs, namely RW 09, RW 10, RW 11, RW 13, RW 15.

Location demographics:

The total population of Cibodas Village consists of 4927 men, 4971 women. With a total of 2981 family heads. Population density 0.13 per km. The livelihoods of the villagers are mostly agricultural laborers, namely as many as 892 male farm workers and 528 female farm workers. There are 699 male farmers in Cibodas Village and 35 female farmers. There are 328 male and 27 female breeders in this village. Meanwhile, 516 men and 127 women engaged in self-employment. There are 41 male traveling traders, and 16 female mobile traders. There are 30 male and 26 female civil servants in Cibodas village. The employees of private companies in this village are 39 men and 11 women. There are 24 small and medium entrepreneurs in Cibodas village and 13 women. There are 2 male and 20 female domestic servants in Cibodas village. The home industry craftsmen in this village are 9 men and 1 woman. There are 8 male mechanics, 3 male TNI members, 2 male artists, and 2 trained village shaman women. There are 1 national police member and 1 male architect, 1 male and 2 female employees of government companies. The total number of working residents is 9842 people.

Potential locations, such as the level of economy and human resources. The main livelihood of Cibodas Village is from the agricultural sector. Especially those with great potential are food crops and plantations. In addition, the forestry potential of this village is quite potential. Another sector that is also very potential to be developed is livestock. The sectors that are less potential to be developed in Cibodas Village are fisheries, mining, industry, rice fields and fruit commodities.

Common obstacles that are often faced in developing village potential are marketing and lack of land. Apart from that, there are other obstacles such as capital and the need for partnership development.

The potential for human resources in Cibodas Village is high. This is related to the livelihoods of the population, which is from the agricultural sector.

Per capita income from residents of Cibodas Village who work in the agricultural sector is IDR 6,420,000 / year. Meanwhile, the livestock sector is IDR 9,600,000 / year. From the service and trade sectors it is IDR 9,850,000 / year. The total family real income in Cibodas Village is IDR 12,967,500 / year.

Environmental Health:

Health facilities and infrastructure are important things in the community environment. In Cibodas Village, there are 17 *posyandu* units each 1 in each RW. The number of active *posyandu* cadres is 85 people plus 2 *posyandu* coaches. In addition, there is also 1 unit of health center, 1 unit of drugstore, and 1 unit of polyclinic. Cibodas Village has 1 dentist, 9 paramedics, 1 trained birth attendant, 6 midwives, and 3 nurses.

Environmental health is also related to the healthy lifestyle of the community. The number of families in Cibodas Village with healthy toilets is 2835 families. Meanwhile, the number of families that have toilets that do not meet health standards is 146 families. In fulfilling the need for clean water, the people of Cibodas Village prefer to subscribe to PAM / BPABS. The number of families who subscribed was 2981 families.

In general, the fulfillment of nutrition for children under five in Cibodas Village is good. The number of well-nourished toddlers is 945 out of a total of 949 toddlers. As for toddlers who experience malnutrition as many as 80 toddlers. Meanwhile, 4 children under five had malnutrition. And 20 toddlers are more nutritious.

Sociological and cultural conditions in the location (including education and health) The majority of Cibodas residents are primary school graduates. The total population of SD / equivalent graduates is 4,768 people, SMP / equivalent graduates 895 people, 611 SMA / equivalent graduates, 28 D1 / equivalent graduates, 14 D2 / equivalent graduates, 15 D3 / equivalent graduates, S1 / equivalent graduates as many as 65 people, and 1 master degree graduate.

The population of Cibodas village who did not complete elementary school was 68 people, 25 people did not complete junior high school, 5 people did not complete high school. Meanwhile, the total population who never went to school was 51 people.

The educational infrastructure in Cibodas Village is 2 Kindergarten units with 4 teaching staff, 5 SD units with 56 teaching staff, 1 SMP unit with 34 teaching staff, and 1 religious education institution with 8 teaching staff and 1 village library unit. As for the art facilities, this village also has the arts of Rock Dangdut, Kacapi Kawih, Pencak Silat, Degung, and Qosidah.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

Religious life

The majority of the population of Cibodas Village is Muslim, namely 4916 men and 4858 women. Other religions embraced by the villagers, namely Christianity as many as 9 men and 8 women, Catholics as many as 2 men and 1 woman, and Buddhism as many as 4 women. The life between religious communities in this village runs in harmony. The religious infrastructure in Cibodas Village is in the form of 23 mosques and 6 prayer rooms.

2. Tourism Potential of Cibodas Village

Potential objects and tourist attractions are the basic capital for the development of a rural area into a tourist village. This potential can be in the form of physical potential of the natural environment and socio-cultural potential (Putra, 2012). Based on this, Cibodas Village has great potential as a tourism village both in terms of the physical potential of the natural environment as well as the socio-cultural potential. Based on the Village profile data in 2016, Cibodas Village area was 988.77 ha consisting of (1) residential area 113.50 ha, (2) 695.27 ha of land, and (3) 180 ha of yards. The total population of the village is 11,206 people consisting of 5655 men and 5551 women. Some types of plants that are the mainstay of farmers are tomatoes, chilies, cabbage, and others. Apart from engaging in agriculture, the villagers are also engaged in animal husbandry.

The livestock which are the prizes of the villagers are cows, free-range chickens, and sheep. The welfare level of the Cibodas village community is quite high. This can be seen from the data on underprivileged families, which only reached 24.8% or 381 families from 1535 families. In addition, the level of community welfare can be seen from the per capita income of each family. Per capita income of the family can be seen from the agriculture, livestock, and small and medium industry sectors.

Based on regional regulation number 14 of 2012 concerning the master plan of tourism development in West Bandung, the tourism potential of Cibodas village can be described as follows:

1. Tourist attraction; the main potential of Cibodas village is agro-tourism, in the form of land and agricultural products (agriculture ranging from nurseries, planting, maintenance, harvesting, and post-harvest; animal husbandry, maintenance, cultivation, and processed livestock products); agricultural special education tours ranging from nurseries to agricultural product processing;
2. Accessibility; the route to the tourist village of Cibodas is adequate but there are still points that need to be repaired; the signs to the tourist village are easily available but are still limited.
3. Facilities; There are 44 homestays available. Each house can accommodate 8-10 people; there is a gift and souvenir center, restaurants, and halls.
4. Community empowerment; Community participation in implementing tourism villages is quite high, however it is still limited to several sectors; the awareness of the people of Cibodas Village has been awakened as a good host in receiving tourists.
5. Marketing and promotion; Promotion is only limited to information from person to person.
6. Institutional and human resources; There is already a regional regulation on the master plan for tourism development in West Bandung (Perda No. 14 of 2012); a community organization that manages a tourist village has been formed. The institution is dominated by the Mekar Tani Jaya farmer group

To develop a strategy for the development of Cibodas tourism village, a SWOT analysis was carried out based on the tourism potential of Cibodas Village. This analysis is conducted to describe the most appropriate strategy in planning the development of a tourism village. The following is an overview of the results of the SWOT analysis and an overview of the strategy.

Based on the results of the SWOT analysis that has been carried out, there are six homestay development strategies that can be done in the development of Wista village, namely;

1. To increase the active participation of the community in tourism village development, starting from the planning, implementation, to program evaluation stages;
2. Development of a distinctive tourism village based on the natural, social and cultural potential of the local community;
3. Capacity building of community institutions as tourism village management institutions (Kompepar) to build coordination and communication between the government, the community and donor agencies;
4. To develop tourism promotion through various media;
5. Enhancing human resources through structured and organized education and training programs;
6. Assistance is carried out in a structured manner from related institutions / offices

The strategies presented above are in line with Law No. 10/2009 concerning Tourism, especially chapter IV regarding Tourism Development Article 7 states that tourism development includes four main components, namely the tourism industry, tourist destinations, marketing, and tourism institutions. Law number 10 of 2009 was followed up by the regional government of West Bandung Regency by issuing regional regulation number 07 of 2013 concerning the Implementation of Regional Tourism. The regional regulation states the main components in the development of regional tourism, namely the tourism industry, destinations, promotions, and tourism institutions.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

Ektrenal	Strength (S)	Weakness (W)
	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Daya tarik objek wisata yang menarik dan alami 2. Sikap masyarakat cenderung ikut berpartisipasi 3. Terdapat kelompok pengelola desa wisata (kompepar) yang dimotori oleh SP4S 4. Keterbukaan masyarakat terhadap pengunjung 5. Fasilitas wisata sudah cukup 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Keikutsertaan masyarakat dalam pengembangan desa wisata masih bersifat pelaksana (Objek belum subjek) 2. Tingkat pendidikan masyarakat masih rendah yang berpengaruh pada keberhasilan pengembangan desa wisata 3. Belum maksimalnya upaya promosi
Opportunity (O)	Strategi SO	Strategi WO
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adanya regulasi dari pemerintah yang mendorong perkembangan pariwisata 2. Adanya kepedulian dari CSR perusahaan dan perguruan tinggi 3. Pasar wisata yang masih terbuka luas 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Meningkatkan partisipasi masyarakat dalam pengembangan desa wisata mulai tahap perencanaan, pelaksanaan, dan evaluasi. (S1+S2+S3+S4+S5+O1+O2+O3) 2. Mengembangkan produk wisata yang khas berdasarkan kepada potensi alam, sosial, dan budaya masyarakat setempat (S1+S4+O1+O2+O3) 3. Pengembangan kapasitas lembaga masyarakat sebagai lembaga pengelola desa wisata (kompepar) (S2+S3+S4+S5+O1) 4. Pengembangan media promosi wisata melalui berbagai media (S1+S2+O2+O3) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Pendampingan kepada masyarakat untuk mengawal proses pengembangan desa wisata (W1+W2+W3+O1) 2. Peningkatan sumberdaya manusia melalui program pendidikan dan pelatihan yang terstruktur (W1+W2+W3+O2+O3)
Threat (T)	Strategi ST	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Kurangnya koordinasi antar SKPD 2. Kurangnya koordinasi antar Pemerintah dengan masyarakat 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Membangun alur komunikasi melalui peningkatan kapasitas kelompok pengembang desa wisata (S2+S3+T1+T2) 	<p>Memberi penyuluhan kepada masyarakat desa wisata mengenai pentingnya pengembangan desa wisata dalam meningkatkan kesejahteraan masyarakat (W1+W2+W3+T 1+T2)</p>

This is also emphasized in the regional regulation of West Bandung Regency number 04 of 2012 concerning the Master Plan for Tourism Development of West Bandung Regency, especially in chapter IV about tourism development strategies, article 11 states that the tourism development strategy is implemented through four development sectors, namely industry, destinations, promotions, and tourism institutions.

The following will describe the Homestay Village development strategy in accordance with the components of regional tourism development;

1. Increasing Participation of Tourism Village Communities Community participation in the development of homestay villages is absolutely necessary. The success of developing a tourist village cannot be achieved without community participation. The local community with their knowledge and experience is a huge asset in carrying out the development of a tourist village. This is in line with Batubara's (2017) opinion that participation is not only one of the goals of social development but is an integral part of the social development process. Community participation means human existence as a whole.

Increasing participation in developing tourist villages must be done by increasing direct citizen involvement in various stages of activities starting from planning, implementation, to program evaluation stages. To build community involvement in a development program, three main elements are needed, namely the willingness, opportunity, and ability to participate. Yuliasuti (2013) argues that the growth and development of community participation in a program depends on the willingness of the community to participate, the opportunities to participate, and the ability to participate.

Willingness to participate is the main key for the growth and development of community participation in the development of tourism village. Sufficient opportunities and abilities are not a guarantee for the growth and development of community participation. If the community has the ability and has been given the opportunity to participate but internally they do not have the will, participation will be low. On the other hand, if abilities and opportunities are limited but have a willingness, it will encourage someone to increase their abilities and actively pursue and take advantage of every opportunity (Yustina and Naria, 2008).

Community participation in the planning stage of tourism village development activities can be seen from the presence of the community in the program planning process carried out by the tourism village manager. The presence of the community in meetings held by the management of the tourism village is sometimes not in accordance with the free time of the invited residents. Community participation in the implementation of activities can be seen from community involvement in physical and non-physical activities, especially in the economic sector. Community participation in the provision of facilities that support the implementation of tourism village development activities is quite good. This can be seen from the high awareness of the community in helping provide tourist facilities such as homestays. In the evaluation phase, community participation can be seen from the attention to maintenance or maintenance on a regular basis at all existing facilities. Community participation in this program is seen from how active the community is in maintaining, maintaining, caring for all existing facilities.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

2. Development of a distinctive tourism village based on the natural, social and cultural potential of the local community

Potential objects and tourist attractions are the basic capital for the development of a rural area into a tourist village. This potential can be in the form of physical potential of the natural environment and socio-cultural potential (Putra, 2012). Based on this, the potential of Cibodas village as a tourist village can be described in terms of the physical potential of the natural environment and the socio-cultural potential as follows. Cibodas area is a hilly area in Lembang District, West Bandung Regency with an altitude of 1260 meters above sea level. The majority of the population earns from agriculture. The commodities in the Caringin Bandung market and the Tangerang main market are vegetable products from Cibodas village which reach around 100 tons / day. About 695.27 ha of fields in Cibodas produce agricultural commodities in the form of vegetables, tubers and fruits. In addition, there are several springs that never dry up, even in the dry season.

Based on the natural and socio-cultural potential of Cibodas village, the development of educational tourism in agriculture has enormous opportunities. The people's desire to obtain entertainment as well as to gain new knowledge is a great opportunity for the development of an educational tourism village. This opportunity occurs because of saturation in the development of education in the room. The learning process in the classroom is rigid and formal so that education in the classroom can create a feeling of boredom or boredom. Therefore, edutainment can be used as an alternative in increasing knowledge, experience, and skills through the entertainment process (tourism). The collaborative process of education and tourism elements can be done through educational tourism activities.

As mentioned in the previous discussion, educational tourism is a tourism concept that presents a combination of the concept of non-formal education with tourism (entertainment) to tourists. In this concept, when tourists visit besides getting entertainment (recreation) they also gain experience / learning with fun methods. In addition, educational tourism is a combination of learning and enriching elements. These two elements are things that must be present in any educational tourism activity. With this concept, tourists have the opportunity to gain new knowledge and experiences as well as enjoyment at tourist objects. Gaining Learning Experience through new knowledge is something that is timeless and can increase one's life or Expansion Life (Kwartolo, 2007).

Based on this concept, the development of an educational tourism village in the Cibodas area can be based on the 3E principle, namely environmental factors, engagement, and exploration (Sharma, 2015: 14-15).

a. Environmental factors (environmental factors) Environmental factors can be in the form of a living atmosphere or learning environment. The environment must be comfortable and can support the smoothness of tourist activities. To create comfort for tourists when doing tourism activities, it must be supported from the physical and social environment. The physical environment is a state that appears around a tourist attraction. Physical environment can be in the form of natural surroundings, cleanliness and environmental health. The social environment comes from the surrounding community, including the attitude of the community in accepting and serving guest visits, friendly attitudes and courtesy, and community attitudes that create a sense of security for tourists. If the physical and social environment is well developed, the development of Wista Village will be easily achieved. This environmental factor will determine the quality of service in the educational tourism village in Cibodas.

b. Engagement; The main goal of someone doing educational tours is to get a learning experience. Therefore, in educational tours tourists must be actively involved in tourism activities. The participation or involvement of tourists in every activity is at the core of the learning process.

Efforts to involve tourists in the learning process are by making tour packages. Tour packages are arranged based on the target group. Therefore, managers must make detailed travel packages based on these target groups. For example, the tour package for the student level will be different from the tour package for the student level or the general public. The packaging of tour packages must be based on the strengths / advantages of educational tourism in agriculture.

c. Exploration (exploration)

Exploration provides direct learning to tourists about the tourist objects that are served. With exploration, tourists can further dig up the information they need, by seeing these objects directly in the field. However, prior to carrying out exploration activities, activities are first conducted to provide guidance to tourists. Briefing is carried out to provide basic knowledge, while exploration will provide deeper knowledge and understanding through experiences gained in the field.

Basically, the exploration process has been designed by the tourism village manager by presenting agricultural tour packages starting from the nursery period to the processing of agricultural products. Through assistance by tour guides and tourism village managers, tourists are presented with various concepts and practices related to the farming process. In this case, in addition to gaining knowledge from the tour guides and tourism village managers, tourists also gain direct experience when participating in farming practices.

3. Capacity building of community institutions as tourism village management institutions (Kompepar). To maintain community acceptance and commitment to tourism activities, strong institutions are needed to control the progress of the tourism development process in the area. In other words, supportive institutions

- 10.00-12.00 Introduction to Cibodas village environment
- 12.00-13.30 Rest, eat, pray
- 13.30-15.00 Introduction of nurseries

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

- Tour guide
Committee
Tour guide, manager

The development and management of a tourist village is a supporting factor for the success of developing a tourist village. Institutions are a place for the community to coordinate and communicate in self-development and group development.

- 15.00-16.00 Committee break
- 16.00-17.30 Introduction to plant maintenance
- 17.30-19.30 Rest, eat and pray
- 19.30-21.00 Bonfire (introduction to cultural arts)
- Tour guide, manager
Committee
Tour guide, manager

Community needs and to solve problems faced by society. The formation of this group is in line with the opinion of Friedman (1993) in Prijono and Pranarka (1996: 138) which explains that the empowerment process can be done individually or collectively (in groups). The organization that has been built in the tourism village development program is the Mekar Tani Jaya Agriculture & Rural Training Center (P4S).

4. Promotion of Tourism through various media

Thus, the promotion in the marketing of tourism products acts as a transaction support by informing, persuading, reminding, and differentiating the promoted tourism product from other tourism. Basically, the tourism manager has an obligation to be able to convey information about various information held by the tourism village, especially tourism potential. Therefore, the management of the tourism village must be careful in choosing communicators to convey messages to the public. Selection of communicators must be based on certain criteria and standards. The criteria and standards are source credibility and resource attractiveness (Saepudin, Budiono, and Rusmana, 2017).

To carry out the promotion process, tourism village managers need to take steps to market tourism products. These steps are identifying tourism products to be marketed, formulating superior products, especially the most attractive and unique products, establishing target markets, formulating positioning, building identity (brand), setting prices, and building marketing communication channels. The following is an overview of the steps that must be taken in promoting a tourism village.

a. Identifying tourism products

Tourism village products are the experiences of tourists during activities in the tourist village. Experience is gained from what is seen, what is done, and what tourists buy. Therefore, the first step that the Wista village manager must take is to identify what tourists can see, do, and buy in the tourist area. The steps to identify rural tourism products are;

- Record as much potential as possible. In the process of collecting data on tourism products, tourism managers should not simply consider a product. No matter how small the potential for tourism products must be identified. This is done because the things that are considered simple and normal in the village are not necessarily taken for granted by visitors. It is possible that ordinary and simple things in the village are extraordinary in the eyes of tourists. For example, growing rice may be commonplace for rural people, but it can be extraordinary for visitors from the city.
- Think innovative. In the process of thinking innovative must be able to make something that does not exist into existence. Therefore, the tourism village manager must be able to see the potential that can be developed according to the interests and motivations of the Wista village visitors. Things that are developed (something new) must be able to meet the expectations of the visitors. For example, making dots for selfies (selfie), making rest facilities with a hammock, making a stage for performances etc.
- Formulating and building superior products. The uniqueness of tourism products must be formulated based on the product identification we have done. The tourism products offered must provide benefits to the targeted tourists. However, in developing this tourism product, you must pay attention to the environmental and social carrying capacity so that the tourism village can continue to develop and be sustainable. The uniqueness that can be sold in Cibodas village is its agricultural environment and agricultural culture, especially learning about agriculture and processed agricultural products.

The composition of tourism products that can be packaged by tourism village managers is physical products, tour packages, and tourism programs. (a) Physical products consist of attractions (natural and artificial) and tourist facilities; (b) A tour package is a combination of several tourist visit destinations for a certain price; and (c) programs are events that can be made by tourism village managers, either on a scheduled basis or spontaneously, such as cooking competitions and processed agricultural products.

- a. Establish a target market
- b. The determination of the target market must be adjusted to the tourism products owned, especially the predetermined superior products. In looking for market segments, tourism village managers can use various segmentation techniques such as segmentation based on tourist destinations, geographic, demographic, psychographic, behavioral or product-based. The targeted segments must pass a selection process and meet the criteria (1) the selected segment must be able to be served by

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

the tourism village manager (product-market matching); (2) the selected segment must show promising growth; (3) the selected segment must be more efficient in reaching it than other segments.

- c. Positioning formulation
- d. Positioning is a strategy in instilling the image of a tourist village in the minds of prospective tourists, so that they are perceived as unique compared to other tourist villages. The basis for determining the positioning is a previously formulated Unique Selling Proposition. Based on the Unique Selling Proposition of Cibodas Village, the majority of the community are vegetable farmers and processed agricultural products, a positioning can be formulated as a center / center for organic vegetables and processed agricultural products in the Lembang area.
- e. Building an identity (brand)
- f. A tourism village must have an identity as a special characteristic and differentiator from other tourism products. A tourism village identity must be unique and easily remembered by the market. In building an identity, the first thing to do is establish a brand (brand). After having a brand, it is then campaigned through marketing communications. According to Keller (2013) in determining a brand, there are several things that need to be considered, namely memorability, meaningfulness, likability, transferability, adaptability, protect ability.
 - (1) Memorability; this means that a brand must be easy to remember, recognize, read, and take center stage.
 - (2) Meaningfulness; brand must have the meaning and essence of the product
 - (3) Likability; the brand must be aesthetically pleasing (eye-catching).
 - (4) Transferability; the brand must be adapted to the language or habits of the market segment.
 - (5) Adaptability; the brand must be flexible or fit in all media, conditions or situations.
 - (6) Protect ability; trademarks should not be imitated or duplicated, therefore they must be legally registered.
- g. Set a price
After the tourism products are packaged, the tourism village manager must calculate the basic costs that must be spent in providing tourism products. This basic cost must be calculated in detail and carefully, whether tourism products are in the form of individual products, packages, or events. Based on the results of the calculation of this basic cost, the tourism village manager can set the selling price for each product. There are several techniques for pricing products to market, namely penetration, psychological, variation. Based on observations in the field, the most appropriate price setting technique for tourism products is the penetration technique. The penetration technique is to set a low price at the beginning to stimulate the visit, and then raise the price until it reaches the normal price position that will be offered regularly.
- h. Building a marketing communication channel
Marketing channel is an intermediary for tourism villages in offering tourism products to potential tourists. There are several channels that can be used by tourism village managers, namely (1) without intermediaries; meaning that the village manager Wista brings in tourists without the help of other parties or intermediaries. This can be done by inviting the community, agencies, or certain communities to come directly to the tourist village location, (2) with the help of intermediaries; means that the manager in bringing visitors through intermediaries such as travel agents, travel agents, guides and others. The formulation of marketing tourism products can be based on the marketing communication model (Sutisna, 2001).

5. Increasing human resources through structured and organized education and training programs:

Increasing the quality of human resources for the management of tourism villages is a form of community empowerment. Therefore, the community empowerment process in developing a tourism village must pay attention to the principles of enabling, empowering, and protecting. Enabling, namely creating an atmosphere or climate that allows the potential of the community to develop; Empowering, namely strengthening the potential or power possessed by the community; and Protecting, namely preventing unbalanced competition, as well as the exploitation of the strong against the weak. These principles must be the basis for developing a tourist village.

The implementation of human resource development in tourism village development can go through the stages of awareness, organizing, and delivery of resources. The process of raising awareness is closely related to the process of community motivation in understanding the potential of themselves and their environment. Resource delivery referred to in this program can be in the form of physical, material, or human resources. The process of delivering resources has been carried out by the Mekar Tani Jaya Self-Help Agriculture and Rural Training Center with a program of mentoring farmers, producers of processed agricultural products, and communities developing other creative economies.

6. Assistance is carried out in a structured manner from related agencies/offices

Assistance in this program is a community empowerment activity by placing assistants who act as facilitators, communicators, motivators, and dynamists. Thus, the mentoring process is an effort to encourage community involvement in developing self-potential and the environment that has been running so far but still has obstacles. Through the mentoring process, it is hoped that independence will occur both individually and in groups. One measure of independence is the community's ability to make decisions.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

V. CONCLUSION

The strategy for developing a homestay in an educational tourism village in Cibodas Village is carried out through six strategies, namely (a) increasing active community participation in tourism village development starting from the planning stage, implementation, to the program evaluation stage; (b) developing a distinctive tourism village based on the natural, social and cultural potential of the local community; (c) capacity building of community institutions as tourism village management institutions (Kompepar) to build coordination and communication between the government, communities and donor agencies; (d) developing tourism promotion media through various media; (e) Increasing human resources through a structured and organized education and training program; (f) Assistance is carried out in a structured manner from related institutions/offices.

The strategies found in this research is applicable limited to Cibodas Village and limited in theme of educational tourism village. Further research should be conducted if the theme would be expanded outside of education.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to express their gratitude to all of people involved in every stages of this research development. To all the key informants in Cibodas Village, each of people who have helped and provided information and funding for this research.

REFERENCES

- 1) Arikunto, S. (2002). *Prosedur Suatu Penelitian: Pendekatan Praktek*. Edisi Revisi Kelima. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 2) Andini, N. (2013). Pengorganisasian Komunitas dalam Pengembangan Agrowisata di Desa Wisata Studi Kasus: Desa Wisata Kembangarum, Kabupaten Sleman. *Journal of Regional and City Planning*, 24(3), 173-188.
- 3) Bittar Rodrigues, C., & Prideaux, B. (2017). A management model to assist local communities developing community-based tourism ventures: a case study from the Brazilian Amazon. *Journal of Ecotourism*, 1-19.
- 4) Bittar Rodrigues, C., & Prideaux, B. (2018). A management model to assist local communities developing community-based tourism ventures: a case study from the Brazilian Amazon. *Journal of Ecotourism*, 17(1), 1-19.
- 5) Blackstock, K. (2005). A critical look at community-based tourism. *Community Development Journal*, 40(1), 39-49.
- 6) Bowler, I., Bryant, C. R., & Cocklin, C. (Eds.). (2002). *The sustainability of rural systems: geographical interpretations* (Vol. 66). Springer Science & Business Media.
- 7) Bramwell, B. (1994). Rural tourism and sustainable rural tourism. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 2(1-2), 1-6.
- 8) Briedenhann, J., & Wickens, E. (2004). Tourism routes as a tool for the economic development of rural areas—vibrant hope or impossible dream?. *Tourism management*, 25(1), 71-79.
- 9) BPS. 2019. Jumlah kunjungan wisman ke Indonesia Februari 2019. <https://www.bps.go.id/.../2019/.../jumlah-kunjungan-wisman-ke-indonesia-februari-2019>.
- 10) Cohen, E. (1972). *Toward a sociology of international tourism*. Social research, New York: Elsevier
- 11) Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Educational research. Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research*. Boston: Pearson Education
- 12) Cawley, M., & Gillmor, D. A. (2008). Integrated rural tourism:: Concepts and Practice. *Annals of tourism research*, 35(2), 316-337.
- 13) Central Java Tourism. 2012. Central Java Tourism - Pariwisata Jawa Tengah. www.indonesia-tourism.com/central-java/
- 14) Dewi, M. H. U. (2013). Pengembangan desa wisata berbasis partisipasi masyarakat lokal di Desa Wisata Jatiluwih Tabanan, Bali. *Jurnal Kawistara*, 3(2).
- 15) Dewi, M. H. U. (2013). Pengembangan desa wisata berbasis partisipasi masyarakat lokal di Desa Wisata Jatiluwih Tabanan, Bali. *Jurnal Kawistara*, 3(2).
- 16) Dimitrovski, D. D., Todorović, A. T., & Valjarević, A. D. (2012). Rural tourism and regional development: Case study of development of rural tourism in the region of Gruža, Serbia. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 14, 288-297.
- 17) Gunn, C. A., & Var, T. (2002). *Tourism planning: Basics, concepts, cases*. Psychology Press.
- 18) Karyono, A. H. (1997). *Kepariwisataaan*. Jakarta: Grasindo.
- 19) Goodwin, H., & Santilli, R. (2009). Community-based tourism: A success. *ICRT Occasional paper*, 11(1), 37.
- 20) Holland, J., Burian, M., & Dixey, L. (2003). Tourism in poor rural areas: Diversifying the product and expanding the benefits in rural Uganda and the Czech Republic.
- 21) Inskeep, E. (1991). *Tourism Planning An Integrated and Sustainable Development Approach*. Willey.
- 22) Kementerian Desa. 2016. Kementerian Desa, Pembangunan Daerah Tertinggal, dan Transmigrasi. <https://www.kemendes.go.id/>
- 23) Kemenpar. 2016. Pembangunan destinasi pariwisata prioritas 2016 – 2019. www.kemenpar.go.id/userfiles/Paparan%20-%20Deputi%20BPDIP.pdf.
- 24) Kemenpar. 2016. Kementerian Pariwisata RI | Siaran Pers: Apresiasi Pesona Destinasi.

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

www.kemenpar.go.id/.../siaran-pers-apresiasi-pesona-destinasi-pariwisata-indonesia-ap

- 25) Kemenpar. 2018. Aplikasi Jaringan Desa Wisata. kemenpar.go.id/asp/detil.asp?id=4162
- 26) Kim, K. H., & Park, D. B. (2017). Relationships Among Perceived Value, Satisfaction, and Loyalty: Community-Based Ecotourism in Korea. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 34(2), 171-191.
- 27) Lane, B., & Kastenholz, E. (2015). Rural tourism: the evolution of practice and research approaches—towards a new generation concept? *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 23(8-9), 1133-1156.
- 28) Mukhtar, P. D., & Pd, M. (2013). *Metode Praktis Penelitian Deskriptif Kualitatif*. Jakarta: GP Press Group.
- 29) Nyoman, S. Pendit. 2002. *Ilmu Pariwisata Sebuah Pengantar Perdana*.
- 30) Nuryanti, W. (1993). *Perspective and Challenges*. Yogyakarta: Gadjah Mada University Press.
- 31) Pendidikan, D. (1989). *Kebudayaan, Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia*.
- 32) Pendit, N. S. (2002). *Ilmu Pariwisata*. Jakarta: Pradnya Paramita.
- 33) Okech, R., Haghiri, M., & George, B. P. (2015). Rural tourism as a sustainable development alternative: An analysis with special reference to Luanda, Kenya. *CULTUR-Revista de Cultura e Turismo*, 6(3), 36-54.
- 34) Pitana, I. G. (1999). Status struggles and the priesthood in contemporary Bali. *Staying local in the global village: Bali in the twentieth century*, 181-201.
- 35) Park, D. B., & Yoon, Y. S. (2009). Segmentation by motivation in rural tourism: A Korean case study. *Tourism management*, 30(1), 99-108.
- 36) Pato, L., Pato, L., Kastenholz, E., & Kastenholz, E. (2017). Marketing of rural tourism—a study based on rural tourism lodgings in Portugal. *Journal of Place Management and Development*, 10(2), 121-139.
- 37) Pawson, S., D'Arcy, P., & Richardson, S. (2017). The value of community-based tourism in Banteay Chhmar, Cambodia. *Tourism Geographies*, 19(3), 378-397.
- 38) Sharpley, R. (2007). Flagship attractions and sustainable rural tourism development: the case of the Alnwick Garden, England. *Journal of sustainable tourism*, 15(2), 125-143.
- 39) Sugiyono, P. (2013). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*.
- 40) Sugiyono (2015). *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi (Mix Methods)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 41) Swarbrooke, J., & Horner, S. (2007). *Consumer behaviour in tourism*. Routledge.
- 42) Stone, L. S., & Stone, T. M. (2011). Community-based tourism enterprises: challenges and prospects for community participation; Khama Rhino Sanctuary Trust, Botswana. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 19(1), 97-114.
- 43) Soemarno, P. D., & Handayani, H. S. (2011). *Desa Wisata*. Malang: PPSUB.
- 44) Spillane, D. J. (1991). *Ekonomi Pariwisata Sejarah dan Prospeknya*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- 45) Sinaga, S. (2010). Potensi dan Pengembangan Objek Wisata Di Kabupaten Tapanuli Tengah. *Jurnal Ilmiah Hospitality Management*.
- 46) Tapiador, F. J. (2007). *Rural analysis and management: an earth science approach to rural science*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- 47) Taylor, S. R. (2017). Issues in measuring success in community-based Indigenous tourism: elites, kin groups, social capital, gender dynamics and income flows. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 25(3), 433-449.
- 48) Undang-undang nomor 32. 2004. Undang-undang nomor 32 tentang Pemerintah Daerah undang-undang republik indonesia nomor 32 tahun 2004 ... - DPR RI.
www.dpr.go.id/dokjdih/document/uu/33.pdf.
- 49) UNWTO. 2001. *Rural Tourism in Europe: Experiences, Development and ...*
<https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/pdf/10.../9789284407163>.
- 50) UNWTO. 2019. *Tourism Direct Gross Domestic Product*. statistics.unwto.org/category/related/unwto.
- 51) WEF. 2016. *The Global Competitiveness Report 2016–2017*.
www3.weforum.org/.../GCR2016.../05FullReport/TheGlobalCompetitivenessReport2016-2017.
- 52) Zakaria, F., & Suprihardjo, R. (2014). Konsep Pengembangan Kawasan Desa Wisata di Desa Bandungan Kecamatan Pakong Kabupaten Pamekasan. *Jurnal Teknik ITS*, 3(2), C245-C249.
- 53) <http://103.229.202.68/dspace/bitstream/123456789/31238/1/Ade%20Suherlan.pdf> diakses pada 20 April 2018 pukul 18.00 WIB INTERNET
- 54) <http://cf.cdn.unwto.org/sites/all/files/docpdf/glossaryenrev.pdf> diakses pada 20 April pukul 15.49 WIB
- 55) <http://media.unwto.org/press-release/2017-08-15/tourism-growth-not-enemy-it-s-how-we-manage-it-counts> diakses pada 9 April 2018 pukul 03.10 WIB
- 56) <http://statistics.unwto.org/sites/all/files/docpdf/glossaryterms.pdf> diakses pada 20 April 2018 pukul 17.30 WIB
- 57) <https://www.bps.go.id/dynamictable/2015/03/06%2000:00:00/807/jumlah-kunjungan-wisatawan-mancanegara-ke-indonesia-tahun-2017.html> diakses pada 5 April 2018 pukul 13.42 WIB

Homestay Development Strategies In Cibodas Village

- 58) <https://www.bps.go.id/statictable/2009/04/14%2000:00:00/1388/jumlah-kunjungan-wisatawan-mancanegara-ke-indonesia-menurut-negara-tempat-tinggal-2017.html> diakses pada 5 April 2018 pukul 15.01 WIB
- 59) <https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/pdf/10.18111/9789284419029> diakses pada 28 Maret 2018 pukul 21.22 WIB
- 60) <https://influencermarketinghub.com/what-is-an-influencer/> diakses pada 9 April 2018 pukul 16.10 WIB
- 61) <https://kbbi.kemdikbud.go.id/> diakses pada 20 April 2018 pukul 00.15 WIB
- 62) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/272014/global-social-networks-ranked-by-number-of-users/> diakses pada 3 April 2018 pukul 13.40 WIB
- 63) <https://www.tripadvisor.com/TripAdvisorInsights/wpcontent/uploads/2018/01/Global-Report-US-Travel-Trends-TripBarometer-2016.pdf> diakses pada 2 April 2018 pukul 19.05 WIB
- 64) <https://wearesocial.com/special-reports/digital-in-2017-global-overview> diakses pada 8 April 2018 pukul 12.47 WIB
- 65) www.kemenpar.go.id/.../Paparan%20-%20Deputi%20BPDIP.pdf diakses pada 5 April 2018 pukul 19.10 WIB
- 66) www.kemenpar.go.id/asp/detil.asp?c=16&id=1652 diakses pada 5 April 2018 pukul 19.58 WIB